

Informed Consent

IRB Number: STUDY2024-0601

Approval Date: 07/11/2024

You are being asked to complete this survey to help a research team at Texas A&M University gather information about offshore energy and tourism on the Texas Gulf Coast.

Information collected will be used to identify public perceptions of the advantages and disadvantages of offshore energy development. Data and findings may be published or presented on by members of the research team. Study outcomes may also be used to inform policymakers and developers about public support or opposition for offshore energy on the Texas Gulf Coast, as well as its potential impacts on tourism and recreation.

Participation in this survey is voluntary. You may wish to participate if you are interested in helping the research team by sharing your experiences or insights. If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to answer a series of questions about energy, tourism, and recreation on the Texas Gulf Coast. You will be compensated the amount you agreed upon with Qualtrics before you entered into the survey. There are no sensitive questions in this survey that should cause discomfort. You may choose to answer or not answer any questions or may stop participation at any time. Your participation in this survey will be kept confidential, and reporting of results will present outcomes in aggregate format. The survey should take about 10 - 15 minutes to complete.

Efforts will be made to limit the use and disclosure of your personal information, including research study and other records, to people who have a need to review this information. We cannot promise complete privacy. Organizations that may inspect and copy your information include the TAMU HRPP/IRB and other representatives of this institution. No direct personal identifiers will be collected.

You may view the survey host's confidentiality policy at: <https://www.qualtrics.com/privacy-statement/>.

Any questions about the survey may be directed to the Principal Investigator, Dr. Jenna Lamphere, at (409) 740-4758 or jlamphere@tamu.edu.

The survey has been reviewed by the Texas A&M University Institutional Review Board. For any questions or concerns about your rights related to participation in this survey, you may contact this group at (979) 458-4067, toll free at 1-855-795-8636, or irb@tamu.edu.

Do you understand the information provided above and wish to participate in this study?

- No
 Yes

We care about the quality of our survey data. For us to get the most accurate measures of your opinions, it is important that you provide thoughtful answers to each question in this survey.

Do you commit to providing thoughtful answers to the questions in this survey?

- I can't promise either way
 Yes, I will
 No, I will not

Energy Industry

In this first set of questions, we would like to ask you about the energy system in the State of Texas.

How informed would you say you are about the energy industry in the State of Texas?

- None at all
- A little
- A moderate amount
- A lot
- A great deal

Do you favor or oppose EXPANDING each of the following sources of energy in the State of Texas?

	Favor	Oppose	Unsure
More offshore oil and gas drilling in U.S. waters	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More onshore oil and gas drilling	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More nuclear power plants to generate electricity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More coal mining	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More solar panel "farms"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More hydraulic fracturing, sometimes called "fracking," for oil and natural gas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More wind turbine "farms"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More biomass or the burning of organic matter for fuel	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Right now, which one of the following do you think should be the more important priority for addressing the State of Texas energy supply?

- Developing alternative sources, such as wind, solar, and hydrogen technology
- Expanding exploration and production of oil, coal, and natural gas
- Both should be given equal priority

Thinking about the State of Texas energy supply, do you think the state government should...

- Phase out the use of oil, coal, and natural gas completely, relying instead on renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power only
- Use a mix of energy sources including oil, coal, and natural gas along with renewable energy sources

And do you think that...

- The State of Texas should never stop using, oil, coal, and natural gas
- The State of Texas should eventually stop using oil, coal, and natural gas, but we aren't there yet

Do you think that the State of Texas should incentivize the production of particular energy types?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes

- Maybe or maybe not
- Probably not
- Definitely not

Please rank the type of energy that you would like the State of Texas to incentivize, with 1 being your top priority.

- More biomass or the burning of organic matter for fuel

- More nuclear power plants to generate electricity

- Offshore wind turbine "farms"

- More onshore wind turbine "farms"

- More offshore oil and gas drilling

- More onshore oil and gas drilling

- More solar panel "farms"

- More hydraulic fracturing, sometimes called "fracking," for oil and natural gas

- Tidal energy or power from the natural rise and fall of the ocean

What is your view on offshore oil and gas production on the Texas Gulf Coast?

- Strongly support
- Somewhat support
- Neither support nor oppose
- Somewhat oppose
- Strongly oppose

Offshore Wind Industry

In this next set of questions, we would like to ask you about offshore wind development on the Texas Gulf Coast.

How aware are you of efforts to develop offshore wind on the Texas Gulf Coast?

- Not at all aware
- Slightly aware
- Moderately aware
- Very aware
- Extremely aware

As you may be aware, in August of 2023, the U.S. Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM) held the first-ever offshore wind energy auction for three wind energy areas (WEA) in the Gulf of Mexico. Shown in Figure 1, the three lease areas included two WEAs off the coast of Galveston and one off the coast of Lake Charles. Only

the Lake Charles WEA sold.

BOEM is proposing a second lease sale, which would include the two Galveston WEAs that did not sell previously, as well as the Port Arthur and Bay City WEAs. All WEAs are located in federal waters, about 30 - 40 miles offshore. Collectively, they total about 410,000 acres.

Figure 1. Wind Energy Area (WEA) Lease Sales

Based on your current understanding, what is your level of support or opposition for the development of offshore wind energy in the four lease areas on the Texas Gulf Coast?

- Strongly support
- Somewhat support
- Neither support nor oppose
- Somewhat oppose
- Strongly oppose

Would you be willing to pay more for electricity if it were generated by offshore wind?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Maybe or maybe not
- Probably not
- Definitely not

Thinking about efforts to develop offshore wind energy on the Texas State Coast, how important is each of the following considerations to you personally?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Getting the state to net-zero carbon emissions as quickly as possible	<input type="radio"/>				
Making sure proposals help lower-income communities	<input type="radio"/>				
Limiting the burden of regulations on businesses	<input type="radio"/>				
Increasing job and economic growth	<input type="radio"/>				
Keeping consumer costs low	<input type="radio"/>				
Protecting the quality of the environment for future generations	<input type="radio"/>				

Thinking about the Texas Gulf Coast **economy**, please indicate the type of impact that you think offshore wind would have for each of the items below.

	Positive Impact	No Impact	Negative Impact	Unsure
Job opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Port activity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Navigation and vessel traffic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Aviation and air traffic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tourism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Commercial fishing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Subsistence fishing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tax revenue	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Property values	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine heritage sites	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Next, thinking about the Texas Gulf Coast **environment**, please indicate the type of impact that you think offshore wind would have for each of the items below.

	Positive Impact	No Impact	Negative Impact	Unsure
Climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Air quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Noise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fish	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine mammals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Seabirds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Migratory birds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Human health	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Aesthetics of seascape	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Last, thinking about the Texas **energy system**, please indicate the type of impact that you think offshore wind would have for each of the items below.

	Positive Impact	No Impact	Negative Impact	Unsure
Energy security	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cost of electricity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reliability of electricity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electrical grid	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oil and gas industry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Energy transmission	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Energy storage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If the U.S. Bureau of Ocean Energy management moves forward with the development of offshore wind on the Texas Gulf Coast, how might you like to get involved? (Check all that apply)

- None (I do not want to get involved)
- Join an email listserv
- Sign a petition
- Respond during a public comment period
- Contribute money to an organization or campaign
- Attend public meetings sponsored by a government agency
- Attend public meetings sponsored by the offshore wind developer
- Attend public meetings sponsored by an advocacy group
- Join a citizen-based advocacy group
- Join a government-sponsored stakeholder/working group
- Other

Maritime Tourism

Because we are especially interested in the potential impacts of offshore wind on tourism and recreation, we have just a few more questions for you about your experiences on the Texas Gulf Coast.

Have you ever visited the Texas Gulf Coast for the purposes of tourism and/or recreation?

- Yes
- No
- I live along the Texas Gulf Coast

In the future, would you be interested in visiting the Texas Gulf Coast for tourism and/or recreation purposes?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

About how many years have you lived along the Texas Gulf Coast? (Please round up to the nearest year)

Where on the Texas Gulf Coast have you visited for tourism and/or recreation purposes? (Check all that apply)

- Galveston
- Port Arthur
- Port Aransas
- Corpus Christi
- Matagorda
- Padre Island
- Other

About how often do you visit the Texas Gulf Coast for tourism and/or recreation purposes?

- More than 5 times per year
- Between 1 and 5 times per year
- Once every 2 years
- Once every 3 to 5 years
- Less than once every 5 years
- Almost never
- Never

When visiting the Texas Gulf Coast, what activities would you engage in? (Check all that apply)

- Visit the beach
- Swim in the ocean
- Eat at a local restaurant
- Depart for a cruise vacation
- Visit a museum
- Go fishing
- Go bird watching
- Take a boat ride (non-cruise vessel)
- View marine life (sea turtles, etc)
- Other

If you visit the Texas Gulf Coast and stay overnight, what is your preferred type of accommodation?

- Campsite
- Hotel
- Vacation rental (Airbnb, Vrbo)
- Friends/family home
- Recreational vehicle (RV)
- Boat
- Other

If offshore wind were developed in the Texas Gulf Coast, which of the below accommodations would you prefer?

- Accommodations with a view of the offshore wind turbines
- Accommodations without a view of the offshore wind turbines
- I am indifferent regarding the view of offshore wind turbines

How much more would you be willing to pay for $\{q://QID60/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$?

- Nothing (I would not pay more)
- \$25
- \$50
- \$75
- \$100
- Over \$100

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Texas Gulf Coast?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I feel a strong sense of community on the Texas Gulf Coast	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think the economy is strong on the Texas Gulf Coast	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel connected to the other people who live on the Texas Gulf Coast	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The Texas Gulf Coast is a special place for me and/or my family	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think the natural parts of the Texas Gulf Coast are beautiful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The Texas Gulf Coast says a lot about who I am	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The Texas Gulf coast is the best place for what I like to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I like the Texas Gulf Coast's mix of plants, animals, and landscapes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If offshore wind energy were developed on the Texas Gulf Coast, would you be interested in taking a tour of it?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

What type of tour would you prefer?

- Onshore information center with telescope and viewing platforms
- An educational guided tour by boat where you can see offshore wind turbines up close
- An unguided tour by boat where you can see offshore wind turbines up close

How much would you be willing to pay for an individual ticket to the boat tour?

- Nothing (I would not pay for a boat tour)
- \$25
- \$50
- \$75
- \$100
- Over \$100

If the boat tour also offered access to offshore recreational activities, would you add the below items to your tour for an additional price?

- Surface water sports (jet skiing, paragliding, wake surfing)
- Fishing opportunities
- None (I would just take the boat tour)

In addition to the $\{q://QID56/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ you said you would pay for an individual ticket to the boat tour, how much more would you pay per individual for the $\{q://QID55/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$?

- Nothing (I would not pay more)
- \$25
- \$50
- \$75
- \$100
- Over \$100

Is there anything else that you would like to share with us about offshore wind and its potential impacts on tourism and recreation?

Demographics

To better interpret the results of our study, in this last section, we would like to ask you a few questions about yourself.

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other

What is your age?

- Under 18
- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 - 84
- 85 or older

How would you describe yourself? Please select all that apply.

- Black or African American
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- White (Non-Hispanic)
- Hispanic
- Other

What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?

- Less than a high school diploma
- High school degree or equivalent (e.g. GED)

- Some college, no degree
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AS)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BS)
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MS, MEd)
- Doctorate or professional degree (e.g. MD, DDS, PhD)

What is your current employment status?

- Employed full time (40 or more hours per week)
- Employed part time (up to 39 hours per week)
- Unemployed
- Student
- Retired
- Homemaker
- Self-employed
- Unable to work

Which of the following categories best describes the industry you primarily work or have worked in?

What is your annual income?

- \$19,999 or less
- \$20,000 to \$39,999
- \$40,000 to \$59,999
- \$60,000 to \$79,999
- \$80,000 to \$99,999
- \$100,000 or more

Which political party do you most closely identify with?

- Republican
- Democrat
- Libertarian
- Independent
- Other

What is the zip code for your primary residence?

